

METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

5 June 2026

Good practice guide

Transfer of calibrations between irradiance transfer standard
spectroradiometer and test array spectroradiometers

A. Seymour^{1*}, Vijeta², P. Caspar³, A. Ferrero⁴, J. Gröbner⁵, P. Kärhä⁶, S. Nevas²,
G. Porrovecchio⁷, C. Rammeloo⁸, T. Schneider⁹, P. Sperfeld², T. Valin¹⁰, R. Zuber¹¹

¹ VSL B.V., The Netherlands;

² Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Germany;

³ Eidgenössisches Institut für Metrologie (METAS), Switzerland

⁴ Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Spain;

⁵ Physikalisch-Meteorologisches Observatorium Davos, World Radiation Center (PMOD/WRC),
Switzerland;

⁶ Aalto University, Finland;

⁷ Czech metrology institute (CMI), Czech Republic;

⁸ National Physical Laboratory (NPL), United Kingdom;

⁹ Instrument Systems GmbH, Germany;

¹⁰ Laboratoire National de Métrologie et d'Essais (LNE), France;

¹¹ Gigahertz Optik GmbH, Germany

* aseymour@vsl.nl

Content

This Good Practice Guide is composed of two reports:

Procedure for the transfer of calibrations between spectroradiometer instruments using narrowband wavelength tuneable spectral irradiance transfer standard light sources

This document develops a procedure for the transfer of calibrations between spectroradiometer instruments using narrowband wavelength tuneable spectral irradiance transfer standard light sources. It will be also be used in a good practice guide for end users that handle transfer standard instruments, and audit their properties with respect to their requirements for recalibration. The good practice guide will provide guidance on how to transfer calibrations from a transfer standard instrument to another array spectroradiometer.

Procedure to transfer spectral irradiance responsivity calibrations among array spectroradiometers using broadband light sources

This document discusses basic principles and procedures for the transfer of the spectral responsivity between array spectroradiometers using broadband light sources. Specifically, the spectral irradiance responsivity of a spectral-irradiance transfer-standard spectroradiometer (ITSS) is transferred to an array spectroradiometer under test (DUT). The aim of the document is to discuss boundary conditions for the transfer including relevant instrumental properties, selection of the source used for the transfer and the measurement conditions. Finally, effect of instrumental properties on the transfer uncertainties are demonstrated based on a few experimental examples and recommendations with respect to auditing instrument properties are given.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Scope

This Good Practice Guide describes procedures for the transfer of calibrations between an irradiance transfer standard spectroradiometer and test array spectroradiometer using broadband and narrowband light sources.

Definitions

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface. The irradiance is expressed in $W \cdot m^{-2}$ (see also CIE S017:2020 ILV, 17-21-053 [CIE 2020 1]).

Spectral irradiance: Density of the irradiance with respect to wavelength. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot nm^{-1}$ (see also CIE S017:2020 ILV, 17-21-056 [CIE 2020 1]).

Broadband light source: A light source whose emission spans a wide range of wavelengths.

Narrowband light source: A light source whose spectral bandwidth is small compared to its central wavelength.

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

Spectral irradiance transfer standard spectroradiometer (ITSS): Spectroradiometer with long-term stability, whose spectral responsivity is traceable to a primary standard (via calibrations), such that it can be used for the dissemination of the spectral irradiance quantity.

Array spectroradiometer under test (DUT): In this document, this is an array spectroradiometer whose spectral responsivity is to be obtained by comparison with ITSS signals.

METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

5 June 2026

Procedure for the transfer of calibrations between spectroradiometer instruments using narrowband wavelength tuneable spectral irradiance transfer standard light sources

Involved partners:
VSL, CMI, CSIC, IS, GGO, METAS, NPL, SFI Davos

Contents

Disclaimer	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. Calibration setup.....	4
3. Model for absolute spectroradiometer calibration of a DUT.....	4
3.1. Spectral bandwidth of source is much larger than the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths	5
3.2. Spectral bandwidth of the source is much smaller than the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths	6
3.3. Spectral bandwidth of the source is similar to the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths..	6
4. Calibration procedure	6
5. Boundary conditions and transfer uncertainties	7
5.1. Combined effect of the bandpass of the instruments and the spectral distribution of the irradiance	7
5.2. Need for the wavelength scale of the DUT	8
5.3. Effect of choice of summation range (IB)	8
5.4. Effect of low SNR signals on the spectral irradiance responsivity of the DUT	8
5.5. Effect of different wavelength sampling	9
5.6. Effect of binning	9
5.7. Integration times	9
5.8. Source stability between measurements with the ITSS and DUT	9
Acknowledgments.....	9
References	10

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Commission, or the European Partnership on Metrology. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. Introduction

This document develops a procedure for the transfer of calibrations between spectroradiometer instruments using narrowband wavelength tuneable spectral irradiance transfer standard light sources from A1.3.1-A1.3.3. For this purpose, the sources developed in WP1 and other typical setups (e.g. monochromatic sources, tuneable lasers, light sources), which are available at the laboratories of VSL, CMI, CSIC, IS, GGO, METAS, NPL or SFI Davos, will be used. The aim is to define boundary conditions and to investigate the achievable transfer uncertainties of the instrument-to-instrument transfer (the target is to reach a combined uncertainty in the spectral irradiance responsivity of array spectroradiometers of 1.0 % ($k = 2$) in the UV, VIS or NIR.)

The output of this activity and A2.4.2 will also be used in a good practice guide for end users that handle transfer standard instruments (A3.3.9), and audit their properties with respect to their requirements for recalibration. The good practice guide will provide guidance on how to transfer calibrations from a transfer standard instrument to another array spectroradiometer.

2. Calibration setup

The spectral irradiance responsivity of an irradiance transfer standard spectroradiometer (ITSS) 0 is transferred to an array spectroradiometer under test (DUT) using narrowband tuneable sources with spectral bandwidths up to a few nanometers, such as the light sources developed in A1.3.1-A1.3.3. The quasi-monochromatic source must be tunable in sufficiently small wavelength steps over the full spectral measurement range of the spectroradiometers with known centroid wavelength and spectral bandwidth at every step. The spectral irradiance distribution of the source must spatially overfill uniformly the entrance optics of ITSS and DUT.

Transfer calibration is performed according to one of the models in Section 3. The source irradiates the entrance optics of the ITSS transfer spectroradiometer, which is set to a selected wavelength reference in a series of steps in the spectral scan described in Section 4. Instrument- and setup-related effects, as well as boundary conditions relevant to the models below, are discussed further in Section 5.

3. Model for absolute spectroradiometer calibration of a DUT

The spectral irradiance values used as reference for transferring calibration from the ITSS to the DUT are obtained by substitution measurements and calculated as signal amplitudes using a spectrally narrowband source. Each wavelength reference is determined as a signal-weighted centroid in the ITSS. In the following subsections, the subscript j denotes the calibration at the j -tuned wavelength of the spectral scan. The subscript i (k) refers to the pixel position in the ITSS's (DUT's) array element corresponding to λ_i (λ_k).

Before performing the transfer calibration, an applicable measurement model must be chosen depending on the source's spectral bandwidth, the instrument spectral bandpass, and the pixel spacing of the spectroradiometers. Accordingly, this section distinguishes between three cases: (i) a broadband like substitution case where bandpass effects are negligible, (ii) the narrow source case in which the signal collapses to a single pixel and can be treated using a line spread function (LSF) method approach [2], and (iii) a general intermediate case requiring explicit bandpass correction.

Figure 1: Illustration of the impact of an instrument's bandpass ($FWHM_{sp}$) and pixel spacing ($\Delta \text{ pix}$), when measuring different spectral bandwidths of a narrowband source ($FWHM_{sou}$). Top left: corresponding to a broadband-like source $FWHM_{sou} \gg FWHM_{sp}$, bandpass effects are negligible and direct amplitude comparison is possible (Section 3.1.) Bottom right: $FWHM_{sou} \ll FWHM_{sp}$ and the signal should be associated to one pixel with a centroid wavelength (Section 3.2.) Top right and Bottom left: the general case where $FWHM_{sou}$ is larger than or similar to $FWHM_{sp}$ (Section 3.3.). $FWHM_{sou}$ was simulated with a triangular function, $FWHM_{sp}$ was simulated using a Gaussian distribution.

3.1. Spectral bandwidth of source is much larger than the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths

In this case, the calibration may be performed as if a broadband, locally flat source was used, and the ITSS and DUT can be calibrated by substitution. The source spectrum is assumed to be locally flat over the instrument bandpass, making the effect of bandpass negligible. If so, no bandpass correction is required.

At each wavelength step in the scan, the count rate signals or signal amplitudes in each pixel, $y_{ITSS,i}$ and $y_{DUT,k}$, is in counts·s⁻¹, and can be compared directly to determine the DUT's unknown spectral irradiance responsivity $s_{DUT}(\lambda_i)$ using the ITSS's spectral irradiance responsivity in each pixel, $s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)$:

$$s_{DUT}(\lambda_i) = \frac{y_{DUT,k}}{y_{ITSS,i}} s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i) \quad (\text{counts} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} / (\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1})) \quad (1)$$

The wavelength scale of amplitudes $y_{ITSS,i}$ has to be interpolated to the wavelength scale of the amplitudes $y_{DUT,k}$, so that both the pixel i in the ITSS and the pixel k in the DUT corresponds to λ_i . Otherwise, errors arise due to the mismatch between the scales should be accounted for as in Section 5.2.

In addition, depending on the ratio of source spectral bandwidth and the spectroradiometer's pixel spacing, the DUT's spectral irradiance responsivity in one or a few pixels surrounding $s_{DUT}(\lambda_i)$ can be calibrated at one setting of j -tuned wavelength λ_j (see Section 5.2.)

3.2. Spectral bandwidth of the source is much smaller than the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths

As illustrated in the bottom right of Figure 1, this is a special limiting case where the spectral bandwidth of the source is narrower than the instrument spectral bandwidths. In this case the signal is associated to a single pixel of the spectroradiometer with a centroid wavelength, λ_j or $\lambda_{DUT,j}$. The method applied here follows the LSF method described in [2], with the ITSS taking the place of the standard trap detector. The ITSS's well characterized reference values of spectral irradiance responsivity is defined in each of its pixels as $s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)$ [3] in counts·s⁻¹/(W·m⁻²·nm⁻¹).

The signal amplitudes in each pixel and the pixel ranges IB_{ITSS} and IB_{DUT} (see Section 5.3) over which to sum the narrowband signals determine the DUT's unknown spectral irradiance responsivity s_{DUT,λ_j} at each wavelength step in the scan. The DUT reading is acquired under the same irradiance conditions as the ITSS (j). The intervals $\Delta\lambda_{ITSS,i}$ and $\Delta\lambda_{DUT,k}$ are the spectral width of an individual pixel and vary across the detector as a function of wavelength.

The model equation for the DUT spectral irradiance responsivity can be written as:

$$s_{DUT,\lambda_j} = \frac{\sum_{IB_{DUT}} y_{DUT,k} \Delta\lambda_{DUT,k}}{E_j} \quad (\text{counts} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} / (\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{nm}^{-1})) \quad (2)$$

The irradiance E_j of the beam illuminating the entrance optics is obtained from the dark corrected ITSS signals with all characterized corrections applied to its readings [4][5][6].

$$E_j = \sum_{IB_{ITSS}} \frac{y_{ITSS,i}}{s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)} \Delta\lambda_{ITSS,i} \quad (\text{W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}) \quad (3)$$

The centroid $\lambda_{DUT,j}$ where the irradiance is defined. See Section 5.2 for further details.

$$\lambda_{DUT,j} = \frac{\sum_{IB_{DUT}} \lambda_k y_{DUT,k}}{\sum_{IB_{DUT}} y_{DUT,k}} \quad (\text{nm}) \quad (4)$$

3.3. Spectral bandwidth of the source is similar to the ITSS and DUT instrument spectral bandwidths

This is the most general and practically relevant case. The instrument bandpass will alter the shape of the measured narrowband source spectrum and affect the measured signal amplitudes due to different spectral weighting over the bandpass. If the ratio of source spectral bandpass to DUT spectral bandpass (measured as their respective FWHM values) is smaller than one or it can be assumed that the DUT spectral responsivity is at most varying linearly over the wavelength range of the spectral bandpasses of source and DUT, the method described in Section 3.2 can be applied. In case non-linear variations of the DUT spectral responsivity are expected on the wavelength scale set by the spectral bandpasses of DUT and source, e.g. due to small modulations caused by etalon effects in the optical path, and the spectral bandpass ratio is larger than one it is advised to apply bandpass correction to DUT measurements. After bandpass correction, the method described in Section 3.1 can be applied.

4. Calibration procedure

To minimize the impact of source instability, the time between measurements performed with the ITSS and the DUT at each wavelength should be kept as short as possible. The wavelength assignment in the DUT may influence the transfer uncertainty and is discussed separately in Section 5.2.

- Define the measurement regime:
 - Determine and fix the source bandwidth,

- Select the calibration model from Section 4 based on source spectral bandwidth with respect to the ITSS and DUT instrument's spectral bandwidth.
- Define the spectral scan:
 - Select the wavelength range and wavelength step size for the transfer of calibration.
- Perform measurements at each wavelength setting λ_j in the spectral range:
 - Set the integration time¹ for ITSS and DUT to operate within their linear response ranges, to avoid saturation and keep a high SNR (often the integration time is adjusted automatically by the operation software of the instrument to achieve signal levels close to the upper end of the instrument linear range),
 - Measure source with ITSS, find dark-corrected $y_{ITSS,k}$, calculate E_j ,
 - Measure source radiation with DUT with its integration time, find dark-corrected $y_{DUT,k}$.
- Assign ITSS measured reference values to DUT signals using the appropriate measurement model and calculate spectral responsivity values for the DUT.
 - If Section 3.3 applies to ITSS and/or DUT measurements, apply bandpass correction to signals.
 - The wavelength λ_j determined from the ITSS measurement may also be assigned to the DUT's signal amplitude.
- Repeat:
 - Repeat the step above for each wavelength λ_j in selected spectral range.
- Interpolate:
 - Interpolate the spectral responsivity values to the full wavelength scale (all pixels within the measurement wavelength range) if necessary. The appropriate interpolation model will depend on the shape of the spectral responsivity.

5. Boundary conditions and transfer uncertainties

The instrument properties of ITSS and DUT should at best be as similar as possible. In this case, the transfer would be closest to a direct substitution measurement and achieve best possible suppression of systematic measurement errors common to ITSS and DUT measurements.

In order to estimate the uncertainty of the transfer calibration, both ITSS and DUT should have well characterized bandpass functions, non-linearity and wavelength scales. The reference planes of the input optics should be well determined. The following effects should be checked, especially if corresponding results of characterizations are not available for the DUT. In any case, uncertainty contributions from the transfer should at best be small compared to the ITSS spectral responsivity uncertainty.

5.1. Combined effect of the bandpass of the instruments and the spectral distribution of the irradiance

The DUT signal used for amplitude assignment in Section 3 is the spectral integral of the convolution of source spectral density with the spectroradiometer bandpass function multiplied by the DUT spectral responsivity. Therefore, the DUT signal must be summed within an adequate interval according to Section 5.3. The spectral bandwidth and the bandpass should be narrow enough for the kinds of spectral distributions to be measured by an end user with the DUT.

Unlike a highly monochromatic laser-based light source, the source bandwidth of the narrowband tuneable sources can be as large as or exceeding the instrument spectral bandwidths of the ITSS or DUT. In those cases, the source spectral bandwidth has to be verified before the calibration measurement because this determines whether Section 3.1 or 3.2 must be applied.

¹ In the case that no access to the integration time is possible (Section 5.7), but irradiance values are adjusted by the company, the value of the integration time is 1.

The effect due to the bandpass function of the spectroradiometer instruments overlaps with the effect due to source bandwidth. When the source bandwidth is smaller than the instrument spectral bandwidths, it is not important to know the bandpass function of the DUT and Section 3.1 or 3.2 applies. However, in Section 3.3 measurements of either ITSS or DUT are instrument bandpass limited. Therefore, the LSFs of the DUT must be measured and correction [3] is needed prior to starting the procedure in Section 4.

5.2. Need for the wavelength scale of the DUT

The methods described in this document rely on either an independent calibration of the DUT's wavelength scale, or assigning it during the responsivity calibration of the DUT.

- If a wavelength calibration of the DUT is already available, differences in wavelengths measured by ITSS and DUT may result. For the “bandpass correction” scenario described in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, the differences have to be accounted for as part of an uncertainty analysis, because here the ITSS data has to be interpolated to the DUT wavelength scale. In the case described in Section 3.2, a spectral integral over the ITSS spectral irradiance output serves as reference value, therefore no interpolation is required and small differences in wavelength scales of DUT and ITSS will typically not lead to significant uncertainty contributions for the spectral responsivity of the DUT.
- If no wavelength calibration of the DUT is available, the wavelength scale of the DUT can be characterized as part of the transfer calibration using the same set of measurement data required for the models in Section 3. Wavelength characterization requires a sufficiently large set of “spectral features” that can be assigned precise wavelength in DUT as well as ITSS data. Those features are naturally available in calibrations using tunable narrow band transfer sources, but typically not in calibrations using broadband sources. Provided responsivity gradients over bandpass are linear and the bandpass function is approximately symmetric, the DUT's spectral irradiance responsivity calibration could be done first in DUT pixel space. Following this, the well-known ITSS wavelength centroids λ_j could be assigned to DUT pixel centroids. The in-band range, IB_{ITSS} , is the spectral range where the counts correspond to the narrowband input power (see Section 5.3.) The power assigned to λ_j using the ITSS as reference has centroid wavelength defined as

$$\lambda_j = \frac{\sum_{IB_{ITSS}} \lambda_i \frac{y_{ITSS,i}}{s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)}}{\sum_{IB_{ITSS}} \frac{y_{ITSS,i}}{s_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)}} \quad (\text{nm}) \quad (4)$$

5.3. Effect of choice of summation range (IB)

The in-band ranges are the spectral range in which the signals corresponding to the spectral input power falls, for the ITSS and DUT measurements. Ideally summations in the measurement model for narrowband sources in Section 3.2 could be performed over the full measurement ranges of the spectrometers. However, in practice there will be some small signal amplitudes also outside the spectral bandwidths of the input spectrum, e.g. due to stray-light or incomplete dark signal correction, which can lead to significant errors for the required spectral integrals if summed up. Therefore, spectral integration/summation is typically performed over an “in-band range” (IB) defined as the minimal spectral measurement range expected to cover the full spectral bandwidth of the input source. Suitable IBs can be estimated e.g. by summing over increasing detector pixel intervals centered around the wavelength with the largest signal amplitude. When the sum changes by less than 0.1% with an increase of the interval width by 2 pixels, the interval can typically be used as an IB suitable for the measurement model.

5.4. Effect of low SNR signals on the spectral irradiance responsivity of the DUT

The inverse of the SNR of the pixel in $y_{ITSS,i}$ with the largest signal should be much smaller than the target relative uncertainty. As an example, when aiming for a standard uncertainty in the DUT's spectral responsivity of 1%, the SNR of the largest signal should be at least 1000. If required, the effective SNR can be increased by taking a series of N measurements under the same conditions and taking the average over all measurements. For typical noise processes the SNR of the average is expected to be \sqrt{N} higher than the SNR of any single measurement. The ITSS and DUT should therefore acquire enough repetitions under the same irradiance conditions with adequate integration time.

5.5. Effect of different wavelength sampling

The wavelength sampling of a specific array spectroradiometer is typically given by sampling imposed by the size of the pixels. However, the ITSS and DUT generally provide different samplings, and it is necessary to modify the sampling of the DUT by interpolation to match the sampling of the ITSS. This interpolation is recommended only at the last stage of the transfer, at the moment when the measured spectral responsivity of the DUT needs to be assigned to the wavelengths for which we have the calibrated value of the ITSS.

5.6. Effect of binning

Binning is the process of using larger pixels by summing signals of several pixels. The positive effect is the increase of the SNR, and the immediate negative effect is the decrease of the spectral resolution through increasing the wavelength sampling step (Δpix in Figure 1). It does not affect the spectral integration within a specific spectral band. If required, it is recommended to apply binning only at the last step of the calibration process on the spectral responsivity of the DUT once it has been determined. However, there are some cases during the characterization where the binning is useful to reduce the noise of the correction factors (for instance, in the characterization of the nonlinearity).

5.7. Integration times

Unless the count signals provided by the ITSS and DUT are automatically normalized by integration time, the integration times must be chosen and tracked for both measurements so that the spectral responsivities will be independent of the chosen integration time. Integration times should be chosen such that the signals fill the linear signal range of detector as much as possible.

5.8. Source stability between measurements with the ITSS and DUT

To minimize the impact of source instability, the time between measurements performed with the ITSS and the DUT at each wavelength should be kept as short as possible. Alternatively, the output of the source should be monitored by an auxiliary detector. The monitor signals can then be used to correct for any variations in source output power between ITSS and DUT measurements.

Acknowledgments

The project 22IEM05 NEWSTAND has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

**EUROPEAN
PARTNERSHIP**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

References

- [1] Ferrero, A., Gröbner, J., Hinken, D., Källberg, S., Nevas, S., Pellegrino, O., Rammeloo, C., Schneider, T., Seymour, A., Sperfeld, P., Valin, T., & Ralf, Z., "Recommendations for instruments requirements, characterization and calibration of array spectroradiometers used as spectral irradiance transfer standard instruments," Zenodo. (2025). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17150796](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17150796)
- [2] Y. Zong, P. S. Shaw, J. P. Rice, and C. C. Miller, "Calibration of spectroradiometers using tunable lasers," CIE x046:2019, 569-574, CIE Central Bureau, Vienna, Austria. (2019). DOI: [10.25039/x46.2019.OP77](https://doi.org/10.25039/x46.2019.OP77)
- [3] Seymour, A., August, L., Ferrero, A., Källberg, S., Kärhä, P., Nevas, S., Pellegrino, O., Porrovecchio, G., Rammeloo, C., Schneider, T., Sperfeld, P., Valin, M. H., Valin, T., Vijeta, Yaran, Ş., & Zuber, R., "Report on the characterisation and calibration of transfer standard spectroradiometers from at least 5 end user applications (to enable the detector-based traceability of spectral irradiance measurements as an alternative to the incandescent lamps-based dissemination of the unit)," Zenodo. (2025). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15634172](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15634172)
- [4] CIE 233:2019 Technical report "Calibration, characterisation and use of array spectroradiometers," (2019). DOI: [10.25039/TR.233.2019](https://doi.org/10.25039/TR.233.2019)
- [5] CIE 250:2022 Technical report "Spectroradiometric measurement of optical radiation sources" (2022). DOI: [10.25039/TR.250.2022](https://doi.org/10.25039/TR.250.2022)
- [6] CIE 214:2014 Technical Report "Effect of instrumental bandpass function and measurement interval on spectral quantities" (2014). DOI: [10.25039/TR.214.2014](https://doi.org/10.25039/TR.214.2014)

METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP

22IEM05 NEWSTAND

5 June 2026

Procedure to transfer spectral irradiance responsivity calibrations among array spectroradiometers using broadband light sources

Involved partners:
PTB, Aalto, GGO, IS, LNE, NPL

Contents

Disclaimer	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Model of evaluation	4
3. Measurement Procedure	5
4. Experimental demonstration.....	5
4.1. Using a QTH lamp	6
4.2. Using LIS-A ²	8
5. Recommendations for auditing the spectroradiometer properties	9
6. Conclusion	10
Acknowledgments.....	10
References	11

Disclaimer

This project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Commission, or the European Partnership on Metrology. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. Introduction

This document discusses basic principles and procedures for the transfer of the spectral responsivity between array spectroradiometers using broadband light sources. Specifically, the spectral irradiance responsivity of a spectral-irradiance transfer-standard spectroradiometer (ITSS) [1] is transferred to an array spectroradiometer under test (DUT). The aim of the document is to discuss boundary conditions for the transfer including relevant instrumental properties, selection of the source used for the transfer and the measurement conditions. Finally, effect of instrumental properties on the transfer uncertainties are demonstrated based on a few experimental examples and recommendations with respect to auditing instrument properties are given.

2. Model of evaluation

The transfer of spectral irradiance responsivity from an ITSS to a spectroradiometer acting as a DUT is based on the fundamental principle of the detector-based substitution. Here, the model of evaluation considers consecutive measurements of a broadband light source with spectral irradiance $E_\lambda(\lambda)$ at the time instances t_{ITSS} and t_{DUT} by the ITSS and the DUT, respectively. The generalized equation can be expressed according to [2] as:

$$S_{DUT}(\lambda_i) = S_{ITSS}(\lambda_i) \frac{y_{DUT}(\lambda_i) E_\lambda(\lambda_i, t_{ITSS}) \prod_{k=1}^n c_{DUT,k}(\lambda_i, t_{DUT})}{y_{ITSS}(\lambda_i) E_\lambda(\lambda_i, t_{DUT}) \prod_{k=1}^n c_{ITSS,k}(\lambda_i, t_{ITSS})}, \quad (1)$$

where

$S_{DUT}(\lambda_i)$ is the responsivity to be calibrated of the DUT at the wavelength assigned to pixel number i of the DUT (in $\text{counts}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}/(\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{nm}^{-1})$)

$S_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)$ is the known responsivity of the ITSS at the wavelength λ_i of the DUT. Since the ITSS and DUT have different wavelengths assigned to the pixels of their detector arrays, the responsivity values of the ITSS need to be interpolated to the wavelengths corresponding to the DUT pixels

$y_{DUT}(\lambda_i)$ is the dark-corrected signal of the DUT at the wavelength assigned to pixel number i of the DUT

$y_{ITSS}(\lambda_i)$ is the dark-corrected signal of the ITSS at the wavelength λ_i of the DUT. Here again interpolation to the wavelengths corresponding to the DUT pixels is required

t_{DUT} is the measurement time with the DUT

t_{ITSS} is the measurement time with the ITSS

$E_\lambda(\lambda_i, t_{DUT})$ is the spectral irradiance at the time t_{DUT}

$E_\lambda(\lambda_i, t_{ITSS})$ is the spectral irradiance at the time t_{ITSS}

$c_{DUT,k}(\lambda_i, t_{DUT})$ is the wavelength-dependent correction factor for the measurement with the DUT at the time t_{DUT}

$c_{ITSS,k}(\lambda_i, t_{ITSS})$ is the wavelength-dependent correction factor for the measurement with the ITSS at the time t_{ITSS}

If the consecutive measurements of the broadband source by the ITSS and DUT are done within a short time interval between t_{ITSS} and t_{DUT} where the source is stable, the measurement equation will be simplified as

$$S_{DUT}(\lambda_i) = S_{ITSS}(\lambda_i) \frac{y_{DUT}(\lambda_i) \prod_{k=1}^n c_{DUT,k}(\lambda_i)}{y_{ITSS}(\lambda_i) \prod_{k=1}^n c_{ITSS,k}(\lambda_i)}. \quad (2)$$

Moreover, the correction factors $c_k(\lambda_i)$ in the nominator and denominator denote spectral corrections required to be applied to the signals of the ITSS and the DUT to correct for the relevant spectroradiometer properties such as nonlinearities, spectral stray light and bandpass, distance setting accuracy (often dominated by the reference plane position), spatial inhomogeneity of the measured light, etc. To derive the correction factors, both the ITSS and the DUT require respective characterizations. The more similar the ITSS and the DUT

spectroradiometers in terms of the respective instrumental properties are, the more similar the corrections are, and they eventually cancel each other out. Conversely, spectroradiometers with different instrumental properties requiring large corrections will result in larger transfer uncertainties.

3. Measurement Procedure

To transfer the spectral irradiance responsivity from an ITSS to a DUT spectroradiometer, following steps are recommended:

1. Perform all relevant characterisations of the spectroradiometer with respect pixel-wavelength assignment, nonlinearity, stray light, bandpass, reference plane position for the entrance optics, etc required to establish the respective correction functions.
2. Select an appropriate broadband source. The spectral irradiance of the source shall be high enough throughout the spectral range of interest enabling the transfer of the calibration from the ITSS to the DUT with an acceptable signal-to-noise ratio. The output of the source must remain stable within the time interval of consecutive measurements by both instruments and have possibly smooth spectrum to minimize bandpass and wavelength mismatch effects on the measured signals. Also, the spatial inhomogeneity of the measured light area shall have negligible effects when measuring with different size entrance optics of the spectroradiometers or it must be corrected numerically.
3. The entrance optics of the spectroradiometers must be aligned in front of the broadband light source for the measurements in such a way that both spectroradiometers measure consecutively at the same position and angular orientation (the entrance plane of the diffusers are perpendicular to the optical axis). Note that the source may irradiate also other surfaces so that the spectroradiometers might be exposed not only to the directly reaching light from the source but also the reflected light (spatial stray light), which leads to errors and must be avoided or eliminated. This can be realised by appropriate baffles etc. or auxiliary measurements to estimate the spatial stray light by blocking the direct view of the source.
4. After the ITSS or the DUT is set and aligned in front of the source, select an optimal integration time for the spectroradiometer to make the measurements with enough repetitions to reduce the noise in the measured signals and to obtain the statistics for the uncertainty analysis.
5. As mentioned above, carry out a measurement to quantify the ambient room stray light by placing a shader in the optical path if required by the setup.
6. Otherwise, make a dark measurement with an internal shutter of the spectroradiometer or an external cover or shutter for the entrance optics.
7. Make an auxiliary measurement to estimate the out-of-range signal contribution if required.

4. Experimental demonstration

Here we present an illustrative example for transferring the spectral irradiance responsivity of a spectral-irradiance transfer-standard spectroradiometer (ITSS) to an array spectroradiometer under test (DUT) via a detector-based substitution. For demonstration purposes, following spectroradiometers [3] were selected:

- **ITSS:** BTS2048-VL-TEC-X, a spectroradiometer manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, with a 2048-pixel thermoelectrically cooled CCD, operating over a spectral range of 280 nm to 1050 nm with a bandpass of 1 nm, with integrated diffuser. The spectroradiometer was characterized with respect to linearity, spectral stray light, optical bandpass, and pixel-to-wavelength assignment wavelength assignment and calibrated for spectral irradiance responsivity.
- **DUT1:** BTS2048-UVVISNIR (Gigahertz Optik), a spectroradiometer manufactured by Gigahertz-Optik, with a 2048-pixel thermoelectrically cooled CCD, operating over a 200 nm to 900 nm spectral range with a bandpass of 2 nm, with integrated diffuser. Like the ITSS, it underwent an independent and comprehensive characterization, deactivating the manufacturer provided calibrations and corrections. The evaluation involved linearity, spectral stray light, bandpass corrections, and pixel-to-wavelength assignments.
- **DUT2:** The CAS-140D UV-VIS by Instrument Systems is built for measurements in spectral range from 200 nm to 830 nm. It features a back-thinned CCD area detector, TE-cooled to -10°C for enhanced stability. The system features a 3 nm spectral bandwidth and an input optics consisting of an OFG424 quartz fiber bundle coupled to an EOP-146 cosine diffuser. The spectroradiometer was fully characterized

for linearity, stray light, bandpass, and pixel-to-wavelength assignment, deactivating the manufacturer provided calibrations and corrections.

To demonstrate the transfer of the spectral irradiance responsivity from the ITSS to the DUT spectroradiometers, two broadband sources were selected: a QTH lamp and an LED-based LIS-A² source that has been developed within the project. The spectral irradiances of both broadband sources are shown in Figure 1 for comparison. Note that spectral irradiance values are not needed for the transfer of the calibration. It is just important that the sources are stable within the short period of time between the measurements by the ITSS and the DUT.

Since, the ITSS and DUTs have different bandpass, it is very important to see how well the transfer from ITSS to DUT propagates proportionally to the difference in bandwidth between ITSS and DUTs using different sources. The QTH lamp as shown in Figure 1 has a very smooth and continuous spectral curve. The spectrum of the LIS-A² source shows LED emission peaks in blue and UV regions.

Figure 1 Spectral irradiance of the quartz tungsten halogen (QTH) lamp and of LIS-A².

Each broadband source was measured consecutively by the ITSS and the two DUTs following the procedure described in chapter 3. Both the ITSS and the DUTs have been characterized for nonlinearity, straylight, bandpass, pixel-to-wavelength assignment, reference plane and the corresponding corrections were applied to measured spectroradiometer signals yielding the spectral irradiance responsivity of the DUTs according to equation 2. The responsivities obtained are compared to the responsivities of the instruments that were derived from a source-based calibration against a standard lamp.

4.1. Using a QTH lamp

The evaluated spectral irradiance responsivity of DUTs with and without bandpass correction via detector-based substitution with QTH lamp was compared with the spectral irradiance responsivity obtained via direct calibration, i.e., source-based calibration against a standard lamp as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT1 (left graph) and DUT2 (right graph) obtained via detector-based substitution with a QTH lamp and direct calibration.

Figure 3 and 4 shows the relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivities of the DUTs obtained via detector-based substitution with QTH lamp (processed both with and without bandpass correction) and direct calibration. For both DUTs, there is just a minor effect of the instrument bandpass on the results because the QTH lamp spectrum and the resulting signals of the DUTs are spectrally smooth. The larger peaks at around 600 nm, 800 nm and 900 nm in the DUT1 signal are caused by the instrument responsivity function rather than the lamp spectrum.

Figure 3 The relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT1 obtained via detector-based substitution with QTH lamp and direct calibration (left axis). The corresponding signals measured by the ITSS and DUT1 are shown on right axis.

Figure 4 The relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT2 obtained via detector-based substitution with QTH lamp and direct calibration (left axis). The corresponding signals measured by the ITSS and DUT1 are shown on right axis.

The good agreement between the transferred responsivity values from the ITSS to the DUTs and those obtained through direct calibration (Figure 3 and 4) confirms that both approaches can be realized with comparable uncertainties.

4.2. Using LIS-A²

The evaluated spectral irradiance responsivities of the DUTs with and without bandpass correction via detector-based substitution with LIS-A² was compared with the spectral irradiance responsivity obtained via a direct calibration, i.e., a source-based calibration against a standard lamp as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 The spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT1 (left graph) and DUT2 (right graph) obtained via detector-based substitution with LIS-A² and direct calibration.

Figures 6 and 7 present the relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivities of the DUTs obtained via detector-based substitution with LIS-A² and direct calibration. Because LIS-A² exhibits distinct spectral peaks below 450 nm, transferring the responsivity from the ITSS (1 nm bandpass) to the lower-resolution DUT1 (2 nm bandpass) and DUT2 (3 nm bandpass), requires bandpass correction. As shown in Figures 6 and 7, the bandpass correction (using Woolliams et al. approach) successfully deconvolves the LED peaks. Beyond the bandpass effects, the responsivity transfer is also sensitive to wavelength misalignments between the TSS and the DUTs. The pixel-to-wavelength assignment directly impacts the results of the detector-based substitution if the source used features steep spectral slopes, which is the case for the LIS-A² spectrum below 450 nm. The presence of the LED peaks and steep slopes renders both accurate wavelength assignment and bandpass correction highly critical, as even marginal shifts in the wavelength scales result in

large deviations. For the wavelengths above 450 nm, the LIS-A² spectrum is smooth yielding results comparable to those from the QTH lamp. Furthermore, the noise artefacts in the measured signals are also susceptible to amplification through the applied bandpass correction.

Figure 6 The relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT1 obtained via detector-based substitution with LIS-A² and direct calibration (left axis). The corresponding signals measured by the ITSS and DUT1 are shown on right axis.

Figure 7 The relative difference between the spectral irradiance responsivity of DUT2 obtained via detector-based substitution with LIS-A² and direct calibration (left axis). The corresponding signals measured by the ITSS and DUT2 are shown on right axis.

5. Recommendations for auditing the spectroradiometer properties

The characteristics of array spectroradiometers may change over time due to ageing (optical components within the instrument, sensor degradation, release of mechanical stress etc.), environmental exposure or damages/changes resulting from handling. Certain properties are more likely to change with time and usage than the others. Table 1 list most important properties of array spectroradiometer and their susceptibility. The spectral responsivity and the pixel-to-wavelength mapping are the two most susceptible properties of the spectroradiometers requiring regular recalibrations. The linearity of the instrument is not expected to change

with time as long as the detection unit is not changed. The spectral stray light properties are also expected to remain stable with time. Nevertheless, note that the stray light characteristics of the spectroradiometer are dependent on the input optics used with the instrument. Therefore, e.g., switching from a diffuser head- to an integrating sphere-based input optics or changing the fibre with different numerical aperture will change the stray light properties of the spectroradiometer involving the need for a recharacterization. The same applies to the bandpass functions and the reference plane of the input optics.

Table 1 Auditing recommendation for the spectroradiometer properties.

Characterization Parameter	Auditing recommendations
Spectral responsivity	Susceptible to ageing and other effects, regular auditing and recalibrations required
Pixel-to-wavelength assignment	May change with time and ambient conditions, regular auditing required
Linearity	Characterization upon initial deployment or any hardware change in the detection unit
Spectral stray light	Characterization upon initial deployment or any change in the hardware of the spectrometer or the input optics
Bandpass function	Characterization upon initial deployment or any change in the hardware of the spectrometer or the input optics
Reference plane	Characterization upon initial deployment or any change in the hardware of the spectrometer or the input optics

6. Conclusion

The successful transfer of spectral irradiance responsivity via detector-based substitution relies on prior characterization of array spectroradiometers (ITSS and DUTs) for nonlinearity, spectral stray light, optical bandpass, pixel to wavelength assignment, reference plane and applying corresponding corrections to spectroradiometer signals. As demonstrated with experimental data, a broadband light source with a smooth and continuous spectrum and sufficient short-term stability is preferred for transferring spectral irradiance responsivity between array spectroradiometers. Utilizing such a broadband source minimizes bandpass and wavelength mismatch errors enabling the transfer of the spectral irradiance responsivity with reduced uncertainties.

Acknowledgments

The project 22IEM05 NEWSTAND has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

**EUROPEAN
PARTNERSHIP**

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

References

- [1] Ferrero, A., Gröbner, J., Hinken, D., Källberg, S., Nevas, S., Pellegrino, O., Rammeloo, C., Schneider, T., Seymour, A., Sperfeld, P., Valin, T., and Ralf, Z., "Recommendations for instruments requirements, characterization and calibration of array spectroradiometers used as spectral irradiance transfer standard instruments," Zenodo. (2025). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17150796](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17150796)
- [2] CIE 233:2019 Technical report "Calibration, characterisation and use of array spectroradiometers," (2019). DOI: [10.25039/TR.233.2019](https://doi.org/10.25039/TR.233.2019)
- [3] Seymour, A., August, L., Ferrero, A., Källberg, S., Kärhä, P., Nevas, S., Pellegrino, O., Porrovecchio, G., Rammeloo, C., Schneider, T., Sperfeld, P., Valin, M. H., Valin, T., Vijeta, Yaran, Ş., and Zuber, R., "Report on the characterisation and calibration of transfer standard spectroradiometers from at least 5 end user applications (to enable the detector-based traceability of spectral irradiance measurements as an alternative to the incandescent lamps-based dissemination of the unit)," Zenodo. (2025). DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15634172](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15634172)